

Socio-Economic Implications of A Vulnerable River “A Case Study of River Dravyavati”

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Abstract

The concept of vulnerability is the inability to resist a hazard or to respond when a disaster has occurred. Assessing water resources vulnerability is the foundation of local water resources management. The research paper attempts to assess the socio-economic implications arising out of vulnerability of Dravyavati River. The Amanishah Nallah, that used to be known as River Dravyavati since antiquity was the lifeline of Jaipur city. Settlements gradually developed along the banks of the river as it has connected many important areas of the city. Ample supply of water for irrigation was also an added advantage. The River once flowing profoundly being frontier now have become a backyard waste dumping zone of those areas making the canal water polluted with foul smell. The unplanned haphazard discharge of untreated household and industrial waste highly polluted the River over the years with diminishing length. In recent times it has turned to a narrow, degraded, congested nullah. The water quality of the river is very poor to maintain a sound river-ecosystem. Moreover various socio economic and anthropogenic factors work as vital role behind the degradation of water channels to contemporary scenario. The main objective of the study is to reveal probe into the present conditions and to highlight the impact of human interference on the river.

The paper aims to summarize physical and human aspects that have catalyzed in degradation of the voluminous river. The task incorporates collating the

Keywords

Vulnerability, Ecosystem, Lifeline, Haphazard, Nallah.

Introduction

The problem of water pollution has proved to be havoc in the Amanishah Nallah environ. It is becoming worse, especially in the last few decades, but seems to be inadequately reported. The city of Jaipur has experienced unprecedented Nallah being silted repeatedly. Besides the silt from eroded/ degraded hills, the Nallah also receives municipal waste, sewage, garbage and untreated industrial effluents from Vishva Karma growth of population and industrialisation beyond optimal limit. Amanishah Nallah passes through densely populated part of Jaipur region. Surface run-off from severely degraded Amer reserve forest and intense gully erosion of areas in upper catchment of Amanishah Industrial (VKI) area; Jhotwara Industrial area, Baisgodam Industrial area, Sanganer textiles tie and dye industries, etc. Pollution of water is correlated with population density and economic growth. There used to be a time when more than Ninety per cent of sewage in the city of Jaipur was discharged into the Nallah untreated. Non-point source pollution from agriculture and urban areas industry point source pollution contribute to the pollutant load. In addition to this, this the anthropogenic activities like irregular and rapid urbanisation, population growth and deforestation have disturbed the natural cycle of hydrology. The concerned imbalance in ecology has resulted in uneven dispersal and pattern of rainfall. The concerned imbalance in ecological has resulted into uneven dispersal and pattern of rainfall. The study area is bound to face dual challenges of depleting and increasing water demand simultaneously. The contamination of water resources has also been increasing due to the development and modernization. Therefore, in terms of the quantity and quality of this vital resource threat has been posed at an alarming rate. Moreover the sustainability of urban environment in the study area has remained questionable as the quality of surface water has impeded the livability of Jaipur city. The main culprit of this issue is the industrial processes working without the administrative consent. The foul smelling of Amanishah Nallah in addition to its insightfulness has been ascribed to the untreated industrial discharge of waste water into it. The ever increasing mosquito breeding around the area is held responsible for making the dwellers vulnerable to health risks. The spillage of waste water in consequent upon the blocked drains continuously increase the cost of repairing of surface roads, hence aggravates the burden on exchequer. The health situation further gets confounded owing to the domestic uses of wastewater and into agriculture. The hotel industry has further aggravated the problem as waste water is let out in a drain connecting to the sewerage network.

Objective of study

The objectives of the research paper are:

1. To have an insight of the impact of human interference on the River and its transformation into a Nallah.
2. To probe into the livability index in the vicinity of the River
3. To suggest some measures to combat the problems faced by the concerned River.

Review of Literature

The literature review herein encompasses chronological and thematic approaches. The review further proves to be an amalgamation of scholarly writings on the studied area well supported by online data base, peer reviewed papers, edited books, dissertations and conference proceedings. Mishra, 1998. was of the view that after independence of the country, the major concerning issue was of reconstruction of economy. The urban scenario of the nation was not provided with much attention and gentrification was worthless to give heed.. Gupta et al,2006.tried to explain the colonial effect on the urban built environment in the post colonial city which were influenced by the views of urban management, planning and perceptions of what remarked proper and rational land management and city development. Jones,2002 discussed that capital cities of our country like Delhi, Begaluru or Kolkata have experienced tremendous growth and the urban planners have failed on the sustainability front. The authority seemingly failed in context to figure out the growth pattern of the cities. The loophole kept on the second line of cities like Ahmedabad and Jaipur in addition to towns as well. Roy,2019 suggested over the vulnerable marginalized sections owing to the rehabilitation process if understood through the lens of the Dravyavati River rejuvenation project, the subject remains unexplored in the Indian scenario. The review aspect in the research has been to the most recent work in this regard as per author's knowledge.

Methodology

Figure1: Study area (Source: JDA, 1990 & JDA, 2011)

Source : Self compiled by the author

The present work is very much dependent on field work and analytic observations. Previous literature has been of much help for getting an overall view of the study areas. The approaches have been landscape and qualitative, descriptive and above all comprehensive discourse analysis.

Table: 1

	Secondary Information / data	Source	Uses
1	Published data of Govt. of India & Govt. of Rajasthan.	The Statistical Abstract (GOI & GOR) 1981-2011	Spatial distribution of sites
2	Rajasthan Govt. Survey Report (GOI), 2001, 2011, 2018	Govt. of Rajasthan	For geochemical and water depth analysis.
3.	Data records of the destinations. (Amanishah catchment)	Official Ward Centres.	For quantification of grim situation to humans, livestock etc.
	Structured no probability sampling method applied.		

Study Area

The capital city of Rajasthan that is Jaipur is highly populated with urban population with the 24. the national growth in the census 2011.Jaipur city is located at 26°55' North and 75°49' East latitude and longitude respectively at an average altitude of 432 m (Dadhich and Hanoka, 2011).

It is the capital and the largest city of Indian state of Rajasthan. There lies 88 per cent decadal growth which is higher in the state and also stands higher than the spatial extension of the city lies to the south of the Amber valley primarily in the heart of eastern Rajasthan. Being covered by fortified hills like the Nahargarh in the north where the palatial Amber and Jaigarh forts are located. Jaipur city has a legacy of well coordinated

architectural planning since antiquity. Architect Vidyadhar Bhattacharya has been credited with the magnificent design and planning of the city. Initially an area of 481 hectares that gradually grew to 670 hectares extended upto the royal boundaries in the form of walls. A time span of four years were taken to complete the squared roads, major palaces, royal structures etc as per the royal guidelines. Roughly to shelter fifty thousand people the city was built and at present the density of population is more than 58,207 person km². (Jain, 2015). Apart from the settlement of Jaipur city, Amber and Sanganer Jaipur Development Authority (JDA) covers the area of outskirts of, Bagru, Chomu, Achrol, Bassi, Shivdaspura and Chandlai Jamwa Ramgarh. The research work attempts to assess the groundwater quality in and the vicinity of Amanishah Nallah, once known as River Dravyavati that used to be the lifeline of Jaipur city. Having fork pattern drainage with river Dhund, at major part of Jaipur city is situated at the confluence zone of the river. The prime target of the research is to reveal the causes of depletion and degradation of the aquifer and its socio-economic and ecological implications.

Limitations

It is a short review based qualitative analytic research. Statistical data based approaches was not inherited in the research process. But this could be a potential future research prospect if analysis processes includes quantitative methods.

Analysis

Water Quality assessment of Amanishah Nallah

The problem of water pollution has proved to be havoc in the Amanishah Nallah environ. It is becoming worse, especially in the last few decades, but seems to be inadequately reported. The city of Jaipur has experienced unprecedented growth of population and industrialisation beyond optimal limit. Amanishah Nallah passes through densely populated part of Jaipur region. Surface run-off from severely degraded Amer reserve forest and intense gully erosion of areas in upper catchment of Amanishah Nallah bring silt in the Nallah. Besides the silt from eroded/ degraded hills, the Nallah also receives municipal waste, sewage, garbage and untreated industrial effluents from Vishva Karma Industrial (VKI) area; Jhotwara Industrial area, Baisgodam Industrial area, Sanganer textiles tie and dye industries, etc. Pollution of water is correlated with population density and economic growth. There used to be a time when more than Ninety per cent of sewage in the city of Jaipur was discharged into the Nallah untreated. Non-point source pollution from agriculture and urban areas and industry point source pollution contribute to the pollutant load. Over the last three decades, water pollution has worsened, affecting almost every part of the city. The physic-chemical testing of samples for the parameters like pH, TDS (Mg/Lit.), Nitrate(Mg/Lit.), Ammonia(Mg/Lit.), Electrical conductivity(μ s/cm),

Total Coliform (CFU/100ml), Alkalinity (Mg/Lit.), Chloride (Mg/Lit.) and Fluoride (Mg/Lit.) was carried out. From the present study, we can see that almost all the drinking water parameters under investigation in the water samples fail to lie within the prescribed or acceptable limit as per BIS or WHO recommendations. Intense supervision is required for the TDS, and nitrate level. From this study, we can recommend that the water samples be treated with lime for neutralising the low pH followed by precipitation or filtration process for removal of fluoride and nitrate. Some parameters may still offer a risk to the consumer.

Fig:2 Water Sampling Stes

Source : Self compiled by the author

Hence apart from the above mentioned water as essential amenity, some other amenities that the residents readily ask and often in no mood of compromise before becoming a part of riparian community are proper sewerage facility, general waste and litter free environment, water availability for irrigation and livestock, STPs etc. The following graph gives the percentage of respondents in the random survey about the above civic amenities on which their satisfactory index was calculated.

Respondents working or living within 500 metres of the riverbank inhabiting within the administrative wards of Bani Park, Civil Lines falling under Vidyadhar Nagar Zone and Mansarover were considered. Moreover Stratified Snowball sampling method was applied to select respondents. With the help of key informants, 80 responses were collected. Oral consent from respondents was taken prior to administering the survey, and participation was voluntary. Three groups of respondents were mainly Senior citizens, Graduate (Male) and Women.

Table 1: Ward-wise distribution of respondents (N=80)

Site	Senior Citizen	Male	Female	Total
Mansarover	10	15	20	45
Bani Park	12	10	10	32
Civil Line	03	05	05	13
Grand Total	25	30	25	80

Source: Field Survey

Satisfaction Index:

On the basis of physical and social disadvantages affecting the well being of the occupants through the immediate surrounding area of the Dravyavati River the satisfaction index has been calculated. Responses were obtained on of castes, different income groups, civic consciousness etc. According to Hall, Yen and Tan (1975), index of satisfaction is calculated and its value ranges between -1 to +1. Positive value of one indicates maximum level of satisfaction different variables related to general waste and litter free environment, water availability for irrigation and livestock ,STPs, sanitation and sewerage facilities in addition to the uninterrupted water supply etc. have been calculated to obtain the of dissatisfaction of the residents. Social disadvantages also have been assessed by taking the opinion of residents on density of population, heterogeneity and vice a versa.

The satisfaction index is derived through the following formula:

$$\text{Satisfaction Index (Is)} = (fs-fd)/N$$

Where,

fs = satisfied respondent

fd = dissatisfied respondent

N = total respondent

Graph: 1 Satkeholder's satisfaction in per cent

From the total 80 respondents/ households, the value of satisfaction index for five parameters surveyed in Dravyavati River environ in administrative wards of Bani Park and Civil Lines and at Mansarover area.

Table: 2

S.No.	Wards	Range of satisfaction Index
1	Bani Park and Civil Lines	0.27 to 0.48
2	Mansarover	0.55 to 0.78

The above table reveals the residents of Mansarover are more satisfied with their quality of living in high rise apartments.

Result and Discussion

Water quality is analysed on the basis of nine parameters. The parameters include total dissolved solid, total hardness, fluoride, nitrate, chloride, sulphide, calcium, magnesium and Iron. It is found from the study that the amount of few constituents has increased in the last five years. Fluoride, nitrate amount has increased in the ground water of district. High amount of both the components are dangerous for human health. It is also observed that the amount of total dissolved solid and total hardness of water beyond permissible limit have increased in the last five year. The amount of Iron is decreased in the last five years in the ground water of Jaipur.

The water quality assessment includes analysis of various constituents present in water and its suitability for usage. In domestic sector the high amount of fluoride and nitrogen affects the health of the people. In Jaipur, there are some areas where the amount of fluoride and nitrogen is beyond the acceptable limit. This is matter of concern because the water can be dangerous for the people in this area. The worthiness of surface water resource is poor whereas the ground water resources are found acceptable in some parts and beyond standards in some area of the district.

Conclusion

The attainment of urban sustainability the removal of encroachment is the need of hour. The immediate and stringent laws in order to ban on disposal of untreated waste in the river should be taken. Moreover planned efforts to check the accelerated run-off and movement of silt from surrounding degraded hills and gully erosion prone areas must be in the priority list. In addition to this the activities like revegetation of gully erosion prone

areas in Amer hills and reviving of existing dams and reservoirs along the river in addition to the construction of more dams/ reservoirs be done. The norms of Pollution Control Board should be considered and the appropriate locations must be fixed for shifting of textile tie and dye industry from Sanganer. The water harvesting can work as catalyst in reviving the under-ground water level if done through abandoned dug wells. Apart from these, green belt plantations of trees and green recreation walkways on both sides of the river to ensure prevention of loss of life, property and groundwater contamination by industrial and sewage effluents shall be a welcome approach. The depleting ground water table in the area may be rejuvenated through activities in the form of growing vegetables/ cash crops and other horticultural activities. Any obstruction in the course of river and zero encroachment should be observed.

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